

Alimurgical Species in Orchards

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Aside their cultural and environmental heritage, locally linked to past food systems, the alimurgical plant species currently represent an opportunity to develop short value chains in rural contexts with high natural values. An interesting strategy at the farm level is the cultivation of alimurgical plants in agroforestry systems. Especially, Mediterranean orchards of various tree species are prone to the alimurgical productions, owing to a wide spacing among the trees and to the recommended practice of greening. In fact, the majority of alimurgical species are poliennial and adapted to coexist with other spontaneous plants. This is why they do not require violent tillage practices. Minimum or no-tillage techniques can be adopted to maintain the soil protected as much as possible through the greening implementation. Given their wild nature, the spontaneous dissemination of these species is often sufficient to preserve over several years the alimurgic productive potential of the orchard. In addition, the light competition between the tree and the herbaceous species is mitigated by the adaptability of the spontaneous herbaceous species to different light environments. Concerning the water economy, the alliance with tree species is beneficial to the spontaneous herbs due to both the tree shadowing and hydraulic lift operated by the deep rooting systems. Finally, the rusticity of the alimurgical species does not require particular fertilization or phytochemical defence, other than that normally applied in the orchard. The harvest of these herbaceous plants usually demands significant labour amounts. However, the added value of such typical products justifies the cultivation in addition to the primary fruit production in the orchard. Agritouristic farms can gain further added value from the alimurgical cultivation, when offering typical alimurgical dishes to their own guests.

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